

BANANA IS A FRUIT OR BERRY AND HEALTH BENEFITS OF BANANAS

Anarbaev Muhammad Pardaboy ugli

Master student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8216575>

Annotation: Sometimes people have questions that surprise them. For example, the question: is a banana a fruit or a berry? The question may also arise: is a banana a grass or a tree? In this article we will consider the essence of these issues.

Key words: Citrus fruits, storage, temperature, humidity, initial quality, storage.

Let's start with the definition of a fruit. Fruit is a concept, most likely, culinary and household than botanical. Fruit refers to all sweet large fruits of plants. Therefore, a banana in everyday life, of course, is a fruit. But a berry in the culinary and everyday concept is all small fruits of plants, so in everyday life a banana cannot be a berry in any way.

In botany, under the word "fruit" the word "fruit" is used. A fruit is a plant reproductive organ that develops from a flower that contains seeds. The fruits are different. One type of fruit is a berry. Botanically, a berry is a plant fruit with a thin skin, juicy pulp and seeds. Store-bought bananas do not have seeds, but wild bananas have black seeds. It turns out that bananas meet these criteria. Bananas are berries.

As for the question of whether a banana is a tree or a grass, everything is simple here. Bananas are giant perennial herbs. Each shoot of a banana bears fruit only once, then it dies, and a new shoot grows in its place.

Useful for the cardiovascular system. Due to the rich content of potassium, bananas have a beneficial effect on the cardiovascular system of the human body, because this mineral is responsible for normalizing blood pressure and stable heart function, thereby significantly reducing the risk of stroke.

Support digestion. Despite the fact that the fruit has a rather sweet taste, bananas belong to foods with a low glycemic index. Bananas are an excellent source of fiber: as

mentioned above, 100 g of banana contains 1.7 g of dietary fiber, which is necessary for regulating the digestive process, as well as for breaking down carbohydrates into simple sugars. This exotic fruit contains pectin, a complex type of fiber that acts as a natural adsorbent: it dissolves in water, binds and removes toxins from the body. The volume of pectins increases as bananas ripen, which is one of the reasons why ripe fruits are much softer.

Slow down oxidative stress. Bananas contain antioxidants (mainly catechins) that protect the body from oxidative processes, are involved in cell repair, slow down the aging process and strengthen the immune system in general. Dopamine, also found in bananas, has antioxidant-like effects, while vitamin C has been linked to healthy skin and a strong immune system.

Beneficial effect on the nervous system. It has been proven that regular consumption of bananas strengthens the nervous system. This is due to the fact that bananas are rich in vitamin B6, and it is a necessary component for the normal functioning of the central and peripheral nervous system. Vitamin B6 is also involved in the regulation of protein metabolism, hemoglobin production, iron metabolism, the synthesis of polyunsaturated fatty acids, and the absorption of amino acids.

Useful for high loads. The unique combination of vitamins, minerals and low glycemic carbohydrates makes bananas a favorite snack for athletes. Eaten before high physical exertion, bananas significantly increase physical endurance. In addition, athletes consume these fruits as a remedy for muscle spasms due to the ability of bananas to maintain potassium levels in the blood.

Important for vision. It is generally accepted that only carrots bring benefits to the eyes, but the use of this tropical fruit also benefits the organs of vision. Bananas contribute to the fight against macular degeneration (retinal damage and impaired central vision) due to the presence of vitamin A in their composition.

References:

1. Busting the seven biggest myths about bananas, источник
2. Boyd W., Lentfer C. «Tracing antiquity of banana cultivation in Papua New Guinea». The Australia and Pacific Science Foundation. September 18, 2007.
3. Dale J. Golden bananas high in Pro-Vitamin A developed, Queensland University of Technology. July 7, 2017
4. A better understanding of bananas could help prevent blindness. American Chemical Society, April 20, 2016,

